

The impact of power network congestion, its consequences and mitigation measures on air pollutants and greenhouse gases emissions. A case from Germany

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Power grid congestion renewables integration
Zonal markets
Redispatching and countertrading
Decarbonization paths
Pollutants and emissions accounting

ABSTRACT

The European power system will have to change significantly in next decades to meet the ambitious targets set by the upcoming European Climate Law. In particular, intermittent renewable energy will be increasingly injected in the system creating potential stability problems. Already in the last five years it has become evident that if the grid expansion does not keep pace with increasing demand for transmission capacity, congestion will happen more and more often in the European power network. To handle congestion, Transmission System Operators extensively use redispatching, requiring individual plants to alter their market-based functioning pattern in order to cope with technical limitations of the network. While the cost of redispatching actions is well known, the change in emission patterns of both greenhouse gases and air pollutants caused by these actions is not, mostly because of a lack of detailed publicly available data. This paper covers such a gap taking Germany as a case study, thanks to the quality of the available data. Following the standard methodology for estimating the direct emissions from fossil fuelled and renewable fed power plants, the study estimates the changes in the emissions of four regulated air pollutants (namely NO_x, SO₂, Particulate Matter and CO) together with those of CO₂ related to redispatching, for the years 2015–2019. The case study of Germany shows how the management of congestions through redispatching does not necessarily imply an increase in the emissions associated with power production in a country, although it has not been possible to complete the study with a full picture of the consequences for other countries emissions because of lack of consistent data.

1. Introduction

The European Power System (EPS) will face at least two important challenges in the next few decades. First, the ambitious greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions reductions targets set in the Climate Law [1]) requires the EPS to abate its emissions at unprecedented rate: according to reference scenarios issued by the European Commission [2] the EPS has to decrease its emissions by about 70–75% in 2030 compared with the 1990 baseline to comply with the overall objectives of –55% in 2030, as the next step for EU reaching carbon neutrality in 2050. To achieve these goals the EPS is expected to increasingly rely on Renewable Energy Sources (RES) most of which are of intermittent nature.

Besides environmental driven changes, another major transformation force for the EPS lays in the continuous implementation of the European single market and the need to overcome the complexities of its still incomplete deployment. The Single European Electricity Market

(SEEM) was initially designed with economic integration and Single Market principles in mind (i.e., increased competition and uniform price for consumers). A single market approach is anyway beneficial even in times of high RES shares: if electricity can flow freely, integration of renewable energy would be greater and easier, reducing the mismatch between production and consumption.

In order for this model to function properly and provide its benefits, congestion has to be avoided as much as possible and should occur only occasionally, in limited quantities and be of a short duration. Unfortunately, such a state is still to be reached and the European electricity system currently has permanent and structural congestions. Causes of this problem rely on the functioning of the market and on the physical limits of the continental transmission grid. Moreover, the concentration of renewable resources far from consumption centres play also an important role in creating congestion.

The EU electricity market is currently based on zonal pricing: the electricity system is divided in geographical zones called bidding zones

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List of abbreviations

CO	Carbon Monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
EDGAR	Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
EPS	European Power System
E-PRTR	European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
mFRR	manual Frequency Restoration Reserve
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides

PM	Particulate Matter
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEEM	Single European Electricity Market
SO ₂	Sulphur Dioxide
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UBA	Umweltbundesamt - German Environmental Authority

Units

GWh	Gigawatthour
MWh	Megawatthour
TWh	Terawatthour
ton/y	tonnes per year
kton/y	ktonnes per year
tons/TWh	tonnes per Terawatthour
tons/GWh	tonnes per Gigawatthour

(usually a bidding zone corresponds to a country with the exception of Italy, Denmark and Sweden) linked by interconnectors. In the day-ahead market electricity is traded assuming infinite transmission capacity inside each bidding zone while the finite interconnector's available capacity is considered for inter-zone trading.

In a second step, TSOs (Transmission System Operators), who have the role of ensuring the operational security of the networks, check if the resulting power flows of the market outcome are feasible. If not, the result is congestion (the resulting power flows exceed the physical capabilities of some power lines), that needs to be resolved to avoid the tripping of the congested power lines, which could in turn lead to disconnection of consumers and generators or even blackouts.

TSOs solve congestions by means of the so-called "remedial actions". Remedial actions are classified in non-costly remedial actions (as for example, changing the topology of the grid) and costly remedial actions (countertrading and redispatching) and have been extensively used in the European power system.

Countertrading and redispatching in particular have the same objective: they decrease the flow upstream of the congestion and increase it downstream to relieve the congestion but they are not implemented in the same way: countertrading mechanisms are operated in the intraday or balancing market (depending on each zone), while redispatching consists of direct modification of the production schedule of certain particular power plants decided by the TSO.

In recent years, the redispatching volume has risen sharply and it is expected that this trend will continue in coming years. The cost of remedial actions in 2019 was 2.25 billion €, nearly half (1.1 billion €) occurring in Germany, although it has fallen over the years (2.60 and 2.82 billion € in 2018 and 2017 respectively) due to a more coordinated approach. The volume of power involved has increased from 51.001 GWh in 2017 to 61.752 GWh in 2019. 91.4% of the redispatched energy was due in order to preserve the internal (intra-zonal) exchanges (see Ref. [3]).

Several causes are responsible for the increase in volume: i) a non-optimal bidding zone delimitation, ii) the change in the electricity mix, i.e. the expansion of renewables generation and at the same time the phase-out of conventional technologies, like coal or nuclear. In the particular case of Germany, wind farms are geographically concentrated in the north of the country with demand, mainly located in southern Germany, increasing power flows from north to south Germany; iii) the delay in grid expansion, which can't follow the pace of new renewable energy installation, iv) the increased volume of international electricity exchange due to the market coupling process.

To avoid the limitation of cross-zonal capacity made available to market participants to solve internal congestions or to accommodate transactions internal to each bidding zone, the new European Electricity

Market Regulation [4] requires that at least 70% of the maximum admissible active power flow has to be given to cross-zonal trade. This means that the reduction of cross-border trading capacities to accommodate "loop-flows" and "internal congestions" as practiced until now, will no longer be permissible in the future. This will also increase the need for redispatching to solve potential larger congestions (see Ref. [5]). Although in the last years there was a cost reduction of remedial actions, the 70% minimum target in combination with the increasing share of intermittent RES generation will increase both the volumes and the costs associated with the application of remedial actions [3].

In the future, power demand increase due to electrification of the transport sector and heating and cooling with the deployment of heat pumps could also lead to significant bottlenecks in distribution networks [6].

2. Literature survey

Feasible pathways for the decarbonization of the European Power System have been recently discussed both by scientists ([7–9]) and international institutions ([10,11]). Generally, all studies show very clearly how the decarbonization of the power system will have to be at the core of any effective emission abatement strategy and has to strongly rely on an important increase of RES quotas.

In 2020 the European Commission has launched a legislative initiative in order for Europe's economy and society to become climate-neutral by 2050. The technical documents accompanying the European Commission proposal aimed at enshrining into law the goal set out in the European Green Deal [12] have confirmed this vision and paved the way for further upcoming regulatory initiatives pushing for fast reaching a zero net emissions European Power System.

Nevertheless, literature has also shown how an increasing quota of intermittent RES poses new challenges ([11,13,14]) including for instance an increasing need for energy storage and an overall change in grid design [15]. As far as grid congestions are specifically concerned, Goop et al. [16] have studied the impact of high shares of renewable energy sources on grid congestion in Europe, finding a positive correlation between solar energy production and delayed (6–9 h) congestions, while wind seems related to longer term congestions. Henni et al. [17] have investigated possible expansion of the Power-to-Gas supply chain as, inter alia, a possible mitigation of RES-cause congestions.

One of the main causes of the surge of network bottlenecks is the delay in the proper development of the electricity grid not being able to keep the pace of the increased flexibility needed when the offer of rapidly intermittent resources increases. This could happen for many reasons: first, the permitting procedure is very long, especially if the line

crosses two different countries. Second, there is often a strong opposition to build new power lines at local level, which usually delays the projects, and finally, these are intensive projects from the financial point of view ([18–20]).

The evolution of European Electricity Markets since the end of the 1990s and the challenges ahead are presented in Ref. [21]. The same authors provide a deep analysis of the rules for the harmonization of national electricity markets and regulations through the EU network codes and guideless in Ref. [22]. Knops et al. [23] evaluate different alternatives for congestion management in the European Power system. The authors consider the following criteria to assess the different redispatching methods: it should be economically efficient in the short-term (day-ahead price) and long-term (provide right economic signals to investments in generation and network), it should be robust to strategic manipulation of the market and it should be transparent. The current inefficiencies due to the interaction between redispatching and the European zonal market design are analysed in Ref. [24]. Redispatching distorts the results of the market coupling in terms of prices (short-term economic signal) and volumes (it results in higher volume of energy exported from congested areas), jeopardizes the business case for demand response and distorts investment signals. It increases the probability of exercising market power and strategic gaming of market participants [25].

A way to increase efficiency is to perform a flow-based regional co-ordinated congestion management [26]. The authors in Ref. [27] present an improvement of the redispatch methodologies to account for network losses, congestion revenues and grid tariffs.

The electrification of transport can increase the congestion problem in case of uncoordinated charge of electric vehicles (EV). On the other hand, EVs can actively support the integration of renewable sources if they can participate in redispatching services [28]. Congestion management can also be improved through active control of the transmission network [29].

A recent study focuses on cost versus market-based procurement of redispatching [30]. Cost-based redispatching makes difficult the participation of demand response while market-based redispatch could increase the strategic bidding in the market which increases the congestion problem and provides wrong long-term economic signals. In the same line of research [31] analyses the cost versus market-based redispatch from the TSO perspective. The authors show how under market based redispatch, the redispatch actions should be based on welfare maximization instead of cost minimization to provide right short-term economic signals.

In summary, current literature provides relevant information on the cost of remedial actions (see e.g. Ref. [25]), an issue that has mainly driven the legislative actions described in the previous paragraph.

By comparison, the impact of network congestion and remedial actions on the emissions of greenhouse gases and air pollutants from the power sector is little known, in our opinion because of the difficulty of acquiring the robust and detailed necessary data.

This study addresses such a gap, estimating the direct emissions of four regulated air pollutants (namely NO_x, SO₂, Particulate Matter and CO) and of CO₂ related to redispatching actions taking place in Germany between 2015 and 2019. In addition, potential emission savings from curtailed wind and solar power have been also estimated for comparison.

To our knowledge, this is the first study addressing in detail the impact of RES curtailment and redispatching on air pollutants and greenhouse gases emissions, across the entire power grid of a large and industrialized country and it could be considered a stepping stone, setting the methodological bases for future studies, provided that data of the same quality will become available.

In fact, the study has been possible because of the availability of good quality and very specific data on redispatching actions collected by German TSOs, although not including details on the redispatching operations taking place in other countries, even when triggered by German

congestions. Moreover, the knowledge of specific emission factors for most of the plants involved in the study has allowed a more precise evaluation of the emissions besides the traditional methodology based on average or typical factors.

The main questions we would like to answer with this work are the following: first, to analyse the generation mix used to perform the redispatching actions. Some authors argue that if redispatching is done after the day-ahead market (curative redispatch), only fast generators can take part, so the most frequent action could be to curtail wind and solar generation upstream the congestion and activating fast gas power plants downwards, giving priority to slow thermal power plants such as nuclear, coal and lignite (so letting these generators aside the redispatching actions), if they co-exist with wind or solar at one side of the congestion [24]. We would like to provide empirical evidence to this statement. Secondly, there is not any work assessing the impact of this practice on emissions and, on summary, to check if redispatching actions are heading in the opposite direction to decarbonization paths.

3. Methodology

The core of the study consists in the analysis of five years of redispatching data collected from German TSOs and the application of emission factors for both air pollutants and GHG gases from different reputable sources. Emissions related to redispatching actions taking place in Germany have been computed for the years 2015–2019 applying emission factors from various literature sources to the redispatching data provided by the German TSOs. Estimates for four air pollutants (namely CO, NO_x, SO₂ and PM) and CO₂ have been calculated, both in absolute terms and per unit of power produced. In formulas, emissions of both GHG and air pollutants have been computed as:

$$E_{p,y,f} = P_{y,f} EF_{p,y,f} \quad (1)$$

where $E_{p,y,f}$ is the amount of pollutant p emitted in year y by the power plants fed with the fuel f measured in ton/y for the air pollutants or kton/y in case of CO₂.

$P_{y,f}$ is the amount of electricity produced in year y using fuel f expressed in GWh or TWh, while $EF_{p,y,f}$ is the emission factor for the pollutant p in the year y generated from fuel f . In this work only direct emissions are computed, meaning no Life Cycle Approach is taken and emission factors for sources with no direct emissions (e.g., solar, wind, nuclear and hydro reservoir and run of river power plants) are set to zero.

Fossil based power plants were grouped into four categories according to the main fuel used: natural gas, lignite, hard coal and liquid. Emission factors for these plants categories have been extracted and, if necessary, properly averaged, from various literature sources (see next paragraph). In the case of power generated by hydro pumped storage power plant, emission factors have been computed on the basis of the source mix active at the moment when water was pumped up to be stored.

It is worth noticing how emission factors are by far the most uncertain parameter in equation (1) and their evaluation is a well-known source of variability and errors whenever emissions are estimated. For this reason different sources for emission factors values have been used in this study with differences between higher and lower emission estimates representing the overall uncertainty.

Unfulfilled (or missed) emission savings of both air pollutants and CO₂ from curtailed wind and solar power have been also calculated for years 2015–2019 on the basis of the emission factors and specific substitution factors¹ provided by the German Environmental Authority

¹ Substitution factors for renewables versus fossil fuels provide an estimate of the fossil fuel mix that would have been used to generate a unit of power actually produced by renewable sources.

(UBA):

$$MES_{p,y,ws} = CP_{y,ws} \sum_f (SF_{y,ws,f} EF_{p,y,f}) \quad (2)$$

where $MES_{p,y,ws}$ is the missed emission saving of pollutant p in year y from wind or solar (ws), $CP_{y,ws}$ is the amount of curtailed electricity in year y from wind or solar, $SF_{y,ws,f}$ is the substitution factor of wind or solar for fuel f in year y and $EF_{p,y,f}$ are the same emission factors used in (1).

These missed emission savings represent the amount of pollutant emissions that would have been avoided if the network had been able to properly dispatch the renewable power that was instead curtailed. Indeed, although mitigation measures, among which redispatching, avoided some curtailment, some renewable power finally had to be curtailed, reducing the amounts of zero emission power injected into the grid. As it was mentioned before, curtailment could also be the result of curative redispatching giving priority of slower reacting thermal power plants such as nuclear, coal or lignite.

3.1. Data sources

- *Redispatching.* Data for Germany were collected from Netztransparenz.de² for years 2015–2019. The dataset provides for each power station involved in redispatching the date and time of the intervention, its duration and its direction (increase or decrease), the average and maximum capacity involved (in MW) as well as the overall resulting generation increase or decrease (in MWh).

- *Emissions from individual power plants.* Annual emissions of both air pollutants and GHG from individual power plants fuelled by lignite and hard coal are available from the data service of Fraunhofer Institute for Solar energy Systems³ for years 2015–2017. The same source also provides data on electricity generated by the same plants.

- *Fossil fuels.* Each power plant reported in the redispatching data has been allocated a fuel category on the basis of the official list of German power plants⁴ and double checked with Open Power System data service⁵ (open-power-system-data.org). Four categories of fossil fuels have been considered: lignite, hard coal, natural gas and mineral oil (liquid). As shown by Ref. [11] the quality of lignite varies considerably between the different German mining districts, resulting in different emission factors. For this reason, the study differentiates the lignite fuelled power plants according to where the lignite is mined: Mitte, Lausatia or Rhein. Lignite quality has been associated to lignite powered plants on the basis of their geographical location.

- *Plant technologies.* According to Ref. [11] emission factors for natural gas fuelled plants depend on the technology employed, differentiating between combined cycle, gas turbine and steam turbine. The technology applied by each natural gas power plant has been retrieved from <https://open-power-system-data.org/>.

- *Average emission factors.* Average or typical emission factors for German power plants are available from several sources. In this paper, emission factors by fuel category were collected from UBA reference publication ([32]) as far as air pollutants are concerned while for CO₂ emission factors from UBA ([33]) and the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR) ([34]) were used. As already stated, only direct emissions have been considered.

- *Specific plant emission factors.* For the subset of hard coal and lignite power plants for which data on both emissions and electricity generated

were available from www.energy-charts.de it has been also possible to evaluate plant level emission factors dividing emissions by power generated.

- *Efficiency.* Average national power plants efficiency has been estimated on the basis of EUROSTAT data of gross electricity generation and fuel consumption for Germany.

- *Renewable energy curtailment.* Data for yearly amount of curtailed wind and solar power has been obtained for years 2015–2019 from Refs. [35,36].

- *Substitution factors.* Substitution factors for wind and solar power in years 2015–2019 have been obtained from the series of UBA reports on Emission balance for renewable energy sources where emissions avoided are calculated for the cited years ([37]).

3.2. Data quality and completeness

Data downloaded from nettransparenz.de comprised 26,980 records. 56 records missed the identification of the involved power plant and were removed from the dataset because of the impossibility of associating reliable emission factors to the reported redispatching actions.

In most of the records, the production change triggered by the redispatching action affects just one power plant, but there are also several records where a group of up to nine power plants, normally of different types, is involved in the production change. In these cases, the production change has been split equally among the plants indicated and the record duplicated a number of times equivalent to the number of plants affected. After this operation, a dataset of 35,655 records of production changes (both increase and decrease) attributed to specific power plants has been obtained.

The association between power plant and fuel has been possible for 33,906 records that made the final dataset for which emissions have been computed. It is worth noticing that, starting from May 1, 2019 there are 1246 items where power plants are identified as “Börse”. This means that the redispatching action was performed considering available resources in the market, and the specific power plant could not be identified. The total amount of energy contracted in the market was 2222 GWh which accounts for 25% of total redispatching energy in 2019.

Power plant emissions are generally available in www.energy-charts.de only for lignite and hard coal plants large enough to report to the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) while nothing is reported for plants fuelled by natural gas and liquids. Consequently, it was not possible to associate a plant specific emission factor to all plants involved in redispatching and gaps have been filled either with average values from fully described plants or using UBA reference data.

A consistency check has been performed between redispatched amounts reported by nettransparenz.de and the data published in ENTSO-E transparency platform.⁶ Unfortunately this data transparency platform currently lacks the information related to the power plants used for the redispatching and countertrading and could not be used to assess emissions.

3.3. Overview of input data

3.3.1. Redispatched power

Fig. 1 shows an overview of the redispatched energy in Germany and its different uses from 2015 to 2019, differentiating between positive (i.e., increased production) and negative (i.e., decreased production) which represent the actions performed downstream and upstream the bottleneck respectively. Increased and decreased power amounts do not match because of the already mentioned incompleteness of dataset and,

² <https://www.netztransparenz.de/EnWG/Redispatch> consulted in May 2020.

³ www.energy-charts.de consulted in May 2020.

⁴ https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/DE/Sachgebiete/ElektrizitaetundGas/Unternehmen_Institutionen/Versorgungssicherheit/Erzeugungskapazitaeten/Kraftwerksliste/kraftwerksliste.html consulted on April 2020.

⁵ <https://open-power-system-data.org/> consulted in May 2020.

⁶ <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/congestion-management/r2/countertrading/show>.

Fig. 1. Services for which redispatching has been used in 2015–2019. Units: GWh (DE-DK1 countertrade relates with the Joint Declaration of the Danish Ministry of Energy, Utility and Climate and the German Economic Ministry signed in June 2017 on increasing the electricity trade between the two countries, starting from January 1, 2019).

more importantly, because redispatching actions performed outside Germany are not reported in the nettransparenz database, even when triggered by German congestions.

As already stated, congestion management is the main reason for redispatching although in 2019 the pattern changed with respect to the previous years and there is significant use of redispatching for voltage control. The redispatching actions used to resolve the congestions between Germany and Denmark before 2018 have been reclassified mainly as countertrading in the intraday market in 2019. In March 2019 the Danish and German authorities (Ministries and National Regulators) signed a joint declaration to gradually increase the available interconnection capacity made available to the day-ahead market between Denmark West (DK1) and Germany bidding zones, from 900 MW up to 1100 MW in 2020 (the initial capacity was 80 MW in 2017, subject to inspection by the European Commission). The TSOs (Energinet from Denmark and Tennet from Germany) shall regularly collect the figures and report them to the authorities to give an overview of total costs, deviations from the target capacities and challenges. Tennet uses the intraday market to procure the energy need to guarantee the capacity made available in the day ahead market (usually ramping-up capacity) whereas Energinet procures the downward volumes in the Nordic mFFR market [38]. It is important to notice that countertrading volumes are contracted in the market without the identification of the specific power plants, so further analysis cannot be performed on this amount of energy.

Fig. 2 shows the balance between internal and cross-border redispatch. Although international trade has increased in recent years and has become a useful mean of incorporating larger amounts of renewable energy production and due to the market integration process at European level, delay in the development of the German internal grid are the main cause of congestions, and internal redispatch has gained importance along the years. It is worth mentioning that countertrading to increase the interconnection capacity between DE and Denmark West in the day-ahead market is mainly attributable to solving internal

bottlenecks in Germany and to not limit the cross-zonal capacity, so it is mainly computed as internal redispatch in Fig. 2 and not as international redispatch.

A detailed analysis of redispatching actions is presented in the supplementary material.

Fig. 3 shows again the amount of redispatched power in Germany in the period 2015–2019 detailing the fuels involved in both decreasing and increasing redispatching. The fuel mix composition of increased and decreased power is very different: lignite power plants are almost only requested to reduce their generation, natural gas almost only increased while hard coal appears in both increasing and decreasing actions and liquid fuels contribute with small amounts to increased production. The effect of reduced energy generated by coal and lignite power plants has two opposite consequences: on the one hand, emissions are reduced by generating less energy, but on the other hand, efficiency is reduced by working at partial loads, which increases emissions per MWh generated. Nuclear is regularly decreased, while hydro and pumped storage contribute to increased power. Biomass plants are generally not involved in redispatching. The mismatch of increased and decreased energy quantities in Figs. 1 and 2 with Fig. 3 for 2019 is due to the fact that 1086 GWh of increasing energy and 1139 GWh of decreasing energy were procured in the market so we could not identify the associated type of generator involved.

In total, redispatching actions resulted in 27.8 TWh decreased and 17.2 TWh increased power production in Germany in the period 2015–2019. It is important to notice that in 2019 the difference between the increased and decreased energy quantities has almost disappeared (a significant reduction is also seen in 2018) which reflects the tendency to solve internal congestions only with internal resources and reducing the request for action by neighbouring TSOs. Nevertheless, the difference is also due, as mentioned above, to the fact that in the case of international redispatch, the counterparty is located in another country. The larger amount of decreasing energy compared to increasing amounts means that congestions mainly happen inside Germany or at interconnections

Fig. 2. Comparison between international and internal redispatching actions. It is important to highlight that the energy need to increase the interconnection capacity between Germany and Denmark is considered as internal redispatching. Units: GWh

Fig. 3. Redispatched power generation in Germany in years 2015–2019, per type of origin and fuel. Units: GWh.

between Germany and neighbouring countries and are solved more often by decreasing production in Germany than in neighbouring countries.

3.3.2. Emission factors

Average emission factors for air pollutants (NO_x, Particulate Matter (PM), SO₂, and CO) and CO₂ are reported in Tables 1–3 for the fossil

Table 1

Average values of specific power plants emission factors from hard coal and lignite power plants in 2015–2017. Units: air pollutants in tons/TWh, CO₂ in tons/GWh (Source: energy-chart.de).

Fuel	2015					2016					2017				
	CO	NO _x	PM	SO ₂	CO ₂	CO	NO _x	PM	SO ₂	CO ₂	CO	NO _x	PM	SO ₂	CO ₂
Hard Coal		614.4		405.2	1066		555.0		353.0	928		505.5		335.0	942
Lignite	322.2	784.0	20.1	575.3	1169	334.6	797.4	19.5	517.9	1173	310.4	785.5	17.4	522.8	1164

Table 2

Average emission factors for air pollutants and CO₂ from fossil fuels. Units: pollutants in tons/TWh, CO₂ in tons/GWh (Source: UBA).

Fuel	Technology	District	CO	NO _x	PM	SO ₂	CO ₂
Natural Gas	Combined cycle	All	61.7	247	2.88	1.26	503
Natural Gas	Steam turbine	All	37.1	358	2.88	1.26	503
Natural Gas	Gas turbine	All	35.4	279	2.88	1.26	503
Liquid	All	All	38.8	919	42.6	701	735
Hard Coal	All	All	58.4	527	13.5	349	887
Lignite	All	Mitte	116.5	725	13.0	872	974
Lignite	All	Rhein	306.6	729	18.0	248	1071
Lignite	All	Lausatia	371.5	746	22.0	706	1053

Table 3

Average emission factors for CO₂ from fossil fuels. Units: tons/GWh (Source EDGAR).

	EDGAR
Natural Gas	531
Liquid	694
Hard Coal	896
Lignite	957

fuels considered in this study. Table 1 shows the average of the plant level emission factors computed for each of the years 2015–2017 based on emission and power production data for single power plants as provided in energy-chart.de, Table 2 shows average emission factors from UBA for both air pollutants and CO₂, while Table 3 shows CO₂ emission factors from EDGAR [34].

3.3.3. Curtailed power and substitution factors

Fig. 4 shows the amount of curtailed wind and solar power in Germany in years 2015–2019 in GWh, while Table 4 shows the substitution factors applied in this study for these two kinds of renewable energy sources. Curtailed wind and solar power amounted in Germany to about 3.5%–4% of the generated solar and wind power between 2015 and 2019, steeply increasing from an average of 1% in the five previous

Fig. 4. Electricity curtailed in Germany in 2015–2019. Units: GWh (Source: EEG in Zhaleh).

Table 4

Substitution factors (%) of wind and solar power for fossil fuelled power (Source: UBA).

	Years	Natural Gas	Lignite	Hard Coal
Solar	2015–2017	41	0	59
Solar	2018–2019	38.6	1.4	60
Wind	2015–2017	39	0	61
Wind	2018–2019	33	2	65

years. Wind power in particular suffered of a curtailment share of about 5%.

4. Results

4.1. Emissions from redispatched power

Emissions of both CO₂ and air pollutants related to the 33,906 redispatching actions performed by a properly identified power plant (see paragraph 3.2) are available in the CSV file included in the supplementary material.

Figs. 5–9 show both the total emissions of CO₂ and air pollutants and emissions per unit of redispatched power from increased and decreased power generation between 2015 and 2019. Figures report the range between the minimum and the maximum estimates obtained applying emission factors values from the different sources presented the previous section. Such a range provides a measure of the variability related to the precise determination of the emission factors and summarizes the overall uncertainties of the study.

In all years examined, emissions for all pollutants and CO₂ from increased power have been smaller than emissions from decreased power, meaning that redispatching management has resulted in an overall decrease in emissions from power production in Germany and emissions avoided from negative redispatching have been higher than actual emissions from positive redispatching.

Two aspects have contributed to this overall effect: as already observed, in 2015–2019 negative redispatching amounted to about 27.8 TWh in Germany while positive redispatching was limited to 17.2 TWh. In practice, the redispatching mechanism moved net production of 10.6 TWh outside Germany and the emissions associated with this extra production were not accounted as German emissions, and instead they have been included in the inventories of the neighbouring countries from which power was increased. Secondly, the generation mix of German positively redispatched power was “cleaner” than the negatively redispatched energy (see bottom panels of Figs. 5–9) because of the differences in the fuel mix so that the German power plants requested to increase production have been on average less polluting per unit of generated power than the ones requested to decrease their power generation.

The less polluting nature of the increased generation is particularly evident for SO₂ because of the large amount of lignite, an important sulphur emitter, present in the decreased mix while largely absent from increased production. Partial substitution of lignite with cleaner natural gas has thus led to an improved emission profile for most of the years considered.

Overall, redispatching actions enabled Germany to avoid emissions of between about 9700 and 14,300 ktons of CO₂, 8600 and 9400 tons of

Fig. 5. Total emissions of CO₂ (upper panel. Units: ktons) and emissions of CO₂ per unit of redispatched power (bottom panel. Units: tons/GWh), both increased and decreased in 2015–2019.

NO_x, 10,500 and 11,300 tons of SO₂, 190–230 tons of PM and 3600–4100 tons of CO in the time span 2015–2019.

Clearly the emission decrease in Germany is partially offset by emission increases taking place in neighbouring countries (NL, BE, CZ, AT, DK, CH, FR and PL) that generated the “missing” 10.6 TWh in Germany. Unfortunately, lack of data made it not possible to evaluate these emissions: so we cannot assess the overall impact of German redispatching measures on the emissions of the overall European emissions.

4.2. Potential emission savings from curtailed power

Tables 5 and 6 show the amount of emissions that could have been potentially avoided with a full injection of the curtailed wind and solar power into the network in 2015–2019, both in absolute value (Table 5) and per unit of power curtailed (Table 6). Estimates are based on

average emission factors from UBA and give a measure of the environmental cost of curtailment, including the congestion related part that mitigation measures have not been able to finally manage.

4.3. Redispatching and curtailment related emissions as shares of national totals

In order to interpret these results, Table 7 shows both total pollutants and CO₂ emissions from the German power sector (1A1a in the IPCC nomenclature [39]) as reported by the European Environmental Agency for years from 2015 to 2018, the last available year.

Fig. 10, obtained from Tables 5 and 7, shows that optimum management of curtailment could have lowered the emissions from power production sectors by a variable fraction between 0.2% and 1.4%, depending on the year and on the pollutant considered. Although such a gain could appear little relevant, it should be recalled that countries

Fig. 6. Total emissions of NO_x (upper panel. Units: tons) and emissions of NO_x per unit of redispatched power (bottom panel. Units: tons/TWh), both increased and decreased in 2015–2019.

adhering to Paris Agreement and to the Convention for Long Range Transport of Air Pollutants are committed to stringent targets for reducing both greenhouse gases and air pollutants, and such a decrease would further support other efforts based on e.g., improving plants efficiency and fuel switching. It is furthermore important to remark that the tendency is clearly upwards, as the percentage of curtailed wind and solar energy is increasing.

Redispatching has indeed partially mitigated the problem, and its mechanism based on coordinated and localized decreases and increases of dispatchable power production has surely avoided a share of curtailment without creating an additional environmental burden to Germany. On the contrary, between 2015 and 2019 positive redispatching has had less impacting both in terms of absolute emissions and emissions per unit of generated power than negative redispatching. Comparing Table 7 with results presented in Figs. 5–9 one can see that redispatching management reduced national German emissions from power production by about 1%, although it should be noted that this result was in part due to the fact that the amount of positive

redispatching taking place outside the country has been higher than the amount of abroad negative redispatching, in fact displacing part of the German emissions to neighbour countries.

Unfortunately, the balance of emissions arising from redispatching taking place outside Germany was not estimated because of lack of information from neighbouring countries. Depending on the power mix the other countries have put in place to cope with redispatching originating in Germany, a complete assessment could both confirm an overall emission decrease, although obviously less relevant than the one estimated for Germany, or could even reverse the sign of the overall balance, leading to an emission increase at the continental scale.

Nevertheless, from a German only perspective, redispatching has allowed the network to accommodate an important amount of emission free power without inducing additional emissions while on the contrary further decreasing them by a small but nevertheless important amount.

Fig. 7. Total emissions of PM (upper panel. Units: tons) and emissions of PM per unit of redispatched power (bottom panel. Units: tons/TWh), both increased and decreased in 2015–2019.

5. Discussion

Congestion and in particular, structural congestion, is increasing in Europe. The Regulation on the internal market for electricity defines structural congestions as “congestions in the transmission grid that are unambiguously defined, predictable and are geographically stable over time, and frequently reoccurs under normal electricity system conditions (see Ref. [4], article 2 (6)).

There are several causes for structural congestion: first, the bidding zone configuration is not reflecting the physical constraints of the grid. Second, the expansion of the electricity network has been always behind the renewable generation enlargement, causing the electricity network to work close to its physical and technical limits. With the continuous expansion of intermittent RES generation, network congestion is becoming greater and more dynamic ([40,41]).

The new Regulation on the internal market for electricity [4] requires the 70% of interconnection capacity shall be made available for

cross-zonal trade. It is expected that this new rule will increase significantly the volume and the cost of remedial actions in the years to come as renewable energy will continue to grow, there will be an increase of international trade as more integration of markets takes place and finally, the delays in network expansion and the increasing demand from sectors being to be electrified in the near future (transport and residential in particular). For the specific case of Germany the reader can consult Annex 1 of [43].

Article 13 of the regulation also sets limits to the total amount of downward redispatching of renewable and high-efficiency cogeneration to a maximum of 5% of their annual generated electricity unless the Member State has already more than 50% of the annual gross final consumption of electricity covered by renewable and high-efficiency generation facilities.

There are two elements impacted for the increasing redispatching and countertrading needs:

Fig. 8. Total emissions of CO (upper panel. Units: tons) and emissions of CO per unit of redispatched power (bottom panel. Units: tons/TWh), both increased and decreased in 2015–2019.

- Although day-ahead prices are decreasing in Europe, the total cost borne by the consumers is increasing. Total cost of countertrading and redispatching is recovered by TSOs passing them on to consumers through network tariffs. For example, in 2019, remedial actions costed 5.67 €/MWh in Lithuania, 2.36 €/MWh in Austria, 2.32 €/MWh in Germany and 1.89 €/MWh in Great Britain.
- The impact of congestion mitigation measures on CO₂ emissions or other pollutant of the system is not however considered, leaving a potential weakness in current efforts to reduce power systems emissions.

As already noted, current redispatching mechanisms are discussed intensively from the economic and market perspective but no work has been done to consider the impact of redispatching on regulated air pollutants emissions of power plants ([44]). Legislative measures applied so far do not consider the environmental dimension of remedial actions and the focus is only on economic efficiency. The results presented in this paper show that the consequences of redispatching on power related emissions are not negligible and could be worth of

consideration in future regulation.

In particular, the presented German case study shows how it is possible, applying a proper redispatching strategy, to solve congestion problems without necessarily increasing national emissions. This was one of the initial research questions, as some authors claimed that depending on the location of congestions, and conventional power plants with respect to wind and solar location, slow thermal power plants should be excluded from the redispatching actions.

We have seen that in the particular case of Germany, coal and lignite power plants are frequently asked to decrease power generation. Nevertheless, even in this apparently positive case some questions remain unanswered. In particular, lack of data has not allowed to evaluate the amount of additional emissions triggered by German congestions taking place in neighbour countries. Moreover, it is also worth noticing that regardless the deployment of redispatching and other remedial actions, a considerable amount of emission free electricity of wind and solar origin is still curtailed in Germany.

Finally, it has to be reminded that the presence of structural congestions increases the risk of strategic gaming from some market

Fig. 9. Total emissions of SO₂ (upper panel. Units: tons) and emissions of SO₂ per unit of redispached power (bottom panel. Units: tons/TWh), both increased and decreased in 2015–2019.

Table 5
Potential emission savings from curtailed wind and solar power in Germany in 2015–2018. Units: CO₂ in ktons, pollutants in tons.

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
CO ₂	3207	2736	4016	4091	4919
CO	235	200	294	297	357
NO _x	1864	1590	2334	2407	2894
PM	43	36	53	56	68
SO ₂	1002	855	1255	1395	1677

participants which in principle could exacerbate the congestions and also increase carbon emissions.

5.1. Limitations of the study and sources of uncertainties

Besides the limitations arising from the lack of information about

Table 6
Potential emissions savings per unit of solar and wind power curtailed in Germany in 2015–2019. Units: air pollutants in tons/TWh, CO₂ in tons/GWh.

	2015–2017	2018–2019
CO ₂	737	763
CO	54	55
NO _x	428	449
PM	10	10
SO ₂	230	260

small but relevant part of the dataset already discussed in section 3, other limitations and possible sources of uncertainties should be addressed.

For instance, in this study the change in efficiency occurring in power plants subject to ramping power up or down to adapt their production to the request of redispatching has not been considered.

Table 7

Emissions from the German power sector in 2015–2018. Units: air pollutants in kttons, CO₂ in Mtons. (Source: European Environmental Agency).

	CO	NO _x	PM ₁₀	SO ₂	CO ₂ (Mtons)
2015	113.9	270.5	6.09	158.4	301.9
2016	110.0	264.5	5.70	138.7	297.8
2017	107.1	251.2	5.34	128.7	276.5
2018	104.0	239.6	5.12	120.9	261.5

Literature reports [16] that thermal power plants working outside their optimal load band, both above and below, are expected to decrease their efficiency and then producing a higher amount of pollutants and greenhouse gases per unit of power generated. Nevertheless, a precise evaluation of the actual changes in efficiency following ramping depend on several factors (speed and direction of the ramping, previous state of the power plant before ramping) unknown in this study.

In the calculation of potential emission savings in curtailment, the substitution factors for whole set of wind power have been applied, while, in principle, the marginal substitution factors for the specific amount of curtailed power should have been applied. In the lack of such an information, it has been presumed that the reported substitution factors provide a reliable approximation of marginal ones.

Finally, it is worth to remind that emission factors for fossil fuel use are a relevant source of uncertainties when producing emission inventories. For this reason in this study intervals instead of single values have been considered whenever possible, using input data as much as possible provided by local institutions.

Although already mentioned, it is important to emphasise once again that the lack of information on actions put in place in other countries to mitigate German congestions have not allowed to provide a complete picture of the impact of German redispatching actions at the European scale. Such a limitation remains unavoidable until the same level of details will be available for power plants participating in mitigating action at the benefit of non-domestic congestions.

6. Conclusions

The results obtained in this paper could help to widen the scope of the current discussion on improving the way power network congestion

is managed in Europe, or in general, in uniform-price (zonal) wholesale electricity markets world regions, subject to a rapid increase of renewable energy generation, which usually involves a slower grid update or development.

This study has overcome the lack of information on environmental consequences of redispatching as a congestion mitigation strategy analysing the “case study” of Germany and has set the basis for further investigations that could be applied to other countries and regions provided data would become available at the same level of detail.

The case study of Germany has shown how, applying a proper redispatching model, where plants involved in negative redispatching are on average more polluting than the ones involved in positive one, has produced benefits for air quality and greenhouse gases emissions, at least inside Germany.

Such an evidence could inspire an update of redispatching strategies and regulations to better addressing the related environmental aspects, especially in consideration of the stringent and ambitious targets European countries are called to respect in coming years. As an example, it should be assured that redispatching leads to benefits also when cross boundary fluxes are considered, an ambition that would benefit from a wider access to properly structured and complete data. A sustainability adder to the redispatching methodologies can create a business case for demand response, or storage units.

The lack of public available data and the inconsistency between the different datasets remains as a barrier for deeper analysis of counter-trading and redispatching.

Credit author statement

Both authors were equally involved in all the phases of the work: conceptualization, data collection, data analysis, paper writing. The original idea of the paper has to be attributed to M.P.B., while F.M.F. identified and provided knowledge of data and methodology for emission assessment.

Disclaimer

The content of this paper reflects the views of the authors only and cannot in any case be regarded as stating an official position of the

Fig. 10. Percentage of national emissions of air pollutants and CO₂ that could be avoided in years 2015–2019 in Germany if curtailed renewable electricity had been able to reach consumers.

European Commission.

Data availability

Emissions of both CO₂ and air pollutants associated with the 33,906 redispatching actions associated to a properly identified power plant (see paragraph 3.2) are available in the CSV file included in the supplementary material.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

We are grateful to our colleague Julian Wilson for the careful revision of the text language.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111501>.

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